

THE EFFECT OF E-COMMERCE ADOPTION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF MICRO, SMALL, AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES MSMEs

RIRIN WULANDARI*¹ and WEI-LOON KOE ²

¹Department of Master of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Mercu Buana, Jakarta, Indonesia. Email correspondence: ririn.wulandari@mercubuana.ac.id

²Department of Business and Management, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan, Melaka, Malaysia.

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine and analyze the effect of e-commerce adoption on the performance of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Jakarta and Melaka, as well as to determine the factors that influence e-commerce adoption. The exact population size is unknown. 141 MSME owners from Jakarta and 111 from Melaka have answered the online questionnaire. Furthermore, the data were analyzed through partial least square-structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM). The results showed that organizational readiness (Jakarta) and management character (Melaka) has an effect on e-commerce adoption. The adoption of e-commerce has a positive and significant effect on the performance of MSMEs. These results are useful for MSMEs in formulating strategies for e-commerce practices, as well as for policymakers in designing strategies to develop and adopt e-commerce in the country. In addition, the findings of this study are the development of the theory of TOE for MSMEs.

Keywords: Adoption, E-commerce, Performance, Micro_Small_Medium_Enterprises

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic that has hit the whole world, including Indonesia, has had an impact on various sectors, including the economy and social order. Social order is related to social distancing, wearing masks, and improving hygiene. Changes in social order mainly prioritize services for limited community movements, most work and activities are carried out from home. So consumer needs also change, from offline purchase transactions to online. Changes in consumer desires need to be met by Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) by adopting e-Commerce to survive and improve their performance. However, there are several problems experienced by MSMEs to adopt e-commerce, so that there are still few MSMEs that have adopted e-commerce, namely in Indonesia only about 13% or about 8 million of the total MSMEs of 62,922,617 million (CNBC, 2020). In Malaysia, MSMEs adopt e-commerce by 20% (Paul Hype Page, 2020). Meanwhile, the economic impact that has occurred on MSMEs due to the Covid 19 pandemic is a 60% decrease in income, even Micro-businesses stop operating by 50% (Kemen KUMKM, 2020). Thus, there is a gap between the increasing need for consumers to transact using e-commerce. Research results by (Ibrahim et al., 2019) show that there is an influence between e-commerce adoption with business continuity, increased sales, and increased profitability. In addition, it affects MSME business strategies (Aizstrauta, 2018), affects financial performance (Sombultawee, 2020), as well as several other benefits that MSMEs have in adopting e-commerce (Lee et al., 2015). Contrary to this opinion, (Thomson et al., 2013) stated that,

although e-commerce adoption can overcome costs, adoption does not always improve performance. Research results by (Ahmed et al., 2018) argued that the adoption of social media does not affect the performance of MSMEs in the UAE. The factors that influence e-commerce adoption are perceptions of obstacles, organizational readiness, and competitor pressure (Ibrahim et al., 2019). Competitor pressure and organizational readiness are also factors that are tested for their influence on e-commerce adoption (Deng et al., 2020), in addition to management support, perceived direct benefits, indirect benefits, and perceived trust. Furthermore, MSME entrepreneurs need to use technology in order to grow rapidly (Kojak, 2011). The perceptions of direct benefits, and perceptions of trust have a positive effect on adoption, however, top management support and organizational readiness do not support e-market adoption (Deng et al., (2020) In addition, organizational and environmental elements influence social media adoption, but management does not affect adoption. Other research shows that performance expectations, effort expectations, facilitated conditions affect the adoption of e-commerce carried out by MSMEs (Sambultawee, 2020)

Based on this explanation, this study aims to determine the factors that affect e-marketing adoption and analyze the effect of adoption on the performance of MSMEs in Jakarta and Melaka. In addition, this study aims to analyze the theory of TAM and TOE on the adoption of micro and small business e-commerce (MSMEs).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theory used to determine variables that affect the adoption of e-commerce is a combination of several theories, namely the Technology Accepted Model (TAM) and The Technology-Organization Environment (TOE)). TAM theory is based on consumers/society reacting to new technology. The two reactions are the perception of ease of use and the perception of usability (Davis, 1989, Fitri & Wulandari, 2020; Chaua & With, 2018; Rahayu & Day, 2015). Technology Organization Environmental (TOE) was formulated to determine the influence of contextual factors that explain and predict the possibilities that occur with the adoption of innovation (Rahayu & Day, 2016; Awa et al., 2016). 3 factors influence companies in adopting innovations or technologies, namely technology, organization, and the external task environment (industry). The TOE concept underlies the selection of technology variable readiness, organization readiness, and character management. These three variables are internal parts of possibilities that occur with the adoption of innovation. Several researchers tested the factors that influence e-commerce adoption, among others (Deng et al., 2020; Kaminski, 2020; Aizstrauta, 2015; Rahayu & Day, 2015), by including the perceived trust variable. From this basis, the perceived trust variable is included in this study.

HYPOTHESIS

Several gaps cause MSMEs to not fully adopt e-commerce, including limited management support, or lack of organizational readiness (Ibrahim, 2019). Organizational readiness affects the adoption of e-commerce by MSMEs (Lim et al., 2018). However, other result show that organizational readiness does not affect e-market adoption by MSMEs (Deng et al., 2020). Based on this, based on this, the hypothesis to be tested is as follows

H1: Organizational readiness have a significant and positive effect on e-commerce adoption

Technology readiness affects e-commerce adoption, according to Aiztrauta, 2015 from the standpoint of technological excellence, (Ahmad et al., 2018; Aiztrauta, 2015) regarding compatibility readiness. According to (Ibrahim et al. (2019) regarding the availability of devices for access. In addition, performance expectations, business expectations, facilitated technology have an effect on e-commerce adoption by MSMEs (Sambultawee, 2020). Based on this, the hypothesis to be tested is as follows:

H2: Technology readiness MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on e-commerce adoption.

The research result of (Fitri & Wulandari, 2020; Chaua & Denga, 2018; Noviarni, 2014), shows that a sense of ease of using new technology determines the acceptance of this novelty. The perceived ease of use is a variable of TAM Theory (David, 2006). The acceptance of technological novelty in this case is the adoption of e-commerce. Based on this, the hypothesis to be tested is as follows:

H3: Perceived ease of use MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on e-commerce adoption.

Perceived usefulness is the user's reaction in the form of perceptions/feelings about the reasons for accepting or rejecting the newness of technology based on considerations of the benefits of technology adoption (Davis, 1989; Fitri & Wulandari, 2020; Rahayu & Day, 2015). Perceive of usefulness dimensions include accelerating sales transactions (Chaua & Denga, 2018), reducing promotional costs (Chaua & Denga, 2018; Odoom et al., 2017; Chaua & Denga, 2018, Thomson et al., 2013), more reaching consumers (Chaua & Denga, 2018; Odoom et al., 2017), and is useful for promoting products/services (Chaua & Denga, 2018; Varshney & Vetter, 2004). The perceived usefulness is a variable of TAM Theory (David, 2006). The acceptance of technological novelty in this case is the adoption of e-commerce. Based on this, the hypothesis to be tested is as follows:

H4: Perceived usefulness MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on e-commerce adoption

Research results by Deng et al. (2020) show that perceptions of direct benefits, perceptions of indirect benefits, perceptions of trust have a positive effect on adoption. Perceived trust is a perception that arises about the behavior of MSMEs trying to avoid risk by believing in the act of accepting adoption. Consumer trust affects purchasing decisions (Punstap & Wulandari, 2020). Purchasing decisions could improve the performance of producers. Another dimension is that e-market and social media are trusted at all times (Deng et al., 2020; Sila, 2013), and e-market and social media provide security guarantees (Deng et al., Awa et al., 2015). Perceived trust has a significant effect on e-market adoption by MSMEs (Deng et al., 2020; Chaua & Denga, 2018; Awa et al, 2013). Based on this, the hypothesis to be tested is as follows:

H5: Perceived trust MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on e-commerce adoption

Some researchers use character management content as a variable that influences the adoption of technological novelties (among others: e-commerce). The dimensions of management

character variables are 1) Awareness; awareness of current conditions and awareness to make changes (Abdillah, 2017; Dorman, 2011), 2) Knowledge (Ghobakhloo & Ching, 2019; Abdilahil et al., 2017; Dormant, 2011; Alharbi, 2008; Tahseen & Sajilan, 2016). Knowledge consists of 2, namely: Knowledge of e-commerce and knowledge to operate, 3) Learning (Abdilahil, 2017; Dormant, 2012), consisting of 2: The desire to learn, acceptance from business owners affects the adoption of e-commerce technology (Arda & Pulungan, 2019). Likewise, management decisions affect e-commerce adoption (Semi, 2012). MSME management is the owner of the business (Demirbas et al., 2011). Based on this, the hypothesis to be tested is as follows:

H6: Management character of MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on e-commerce adoption

Research results by Ibrahim et al. (2019) show that there is an influence between e-commerce adoptions with business continuity, increased sales, and increased profitability. In addition, it affects MSME business strategies (Aizstrauta, 2018), affects financial performance (Sombultawee, 2020), as well as several other benefits that MSMEs have in adopting e-commerce (Lee et al., 2015). In addition, it affects MSME business strategies (Aizstrauta, 2018), affects financial performance (Sombultawee, 2020), as well as several other benefits that MSMEs have in adopting e-commerce (Lee et al., 2015). Contrary to this opinion, Thomson et al. (2013) stated that, although e-commerce adoption can overcome costs, adoption does not always improve performance. Research results argued that the adoption of social media does not affect the performance of MSMEs in the UA (Ahmed et al., 2018). Based on this, the hypothesis to be tested is as follows:

H7: Adoption of e-commerce by MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on MSMEs performance

FRAMEWORK

Based on the above explanation, the research framework is presented as follows (Figure 1. Framework).

Figure 1: Framework

METHODS

Research locations in Jakarta and Melaka. The population in this study is Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Jakarta and Melaka, from various types of businesses. The number of samples was determined based on the number of arrows from exogenous variables to endogenous variables in the model framework. For 7 arrows, a minimum sample of 80 respondents (Yahaya, 2019). Thus the sample of this research is quite adequate, namely the sample in Jakarta as many as --141. The number of respondents in Melaka is 111 respondents. The independent research variables (exogenous) consist of X1 organizational readiness, X2 technology readiness, X3 perceived ease of use, X4 perceived usefulness, X5 perceived trust, X6 management character. The dependent variable (endogenous) consists of e-commerce adoption, Z1, and performance of MSMEs, Y1.

RESULT

Profile Analysis

In Jakarta, respondents were dominated by micro-companies with employees 1-4, at 75.9%, small companies at 17.7%, and medium enterprises at 6.4%. Companies that do not have a business entity or individual are 63.8%, Limited Liability Company (PT) is 18.4%, Partnership is 14.2%, and CV is 3.5%. The largest number of types of business is production at 47.5%. Furthermore, Trade as much as 18.4%, Others 10.6%, Services 5.7%, and Plantation, Agriculture, Fishery, Stockbreeding as much as 4.3%.

In Melaka, respondents were dominated by small companies with employees 5-74, at 65.8%, micro-companies at 34.2%. The larger number of types of business services, at 66.7%, production at 27%, other at 6.3%. Companies that do not have a business entity or individual are 35.2%, Limited Liability Company (PT) is 30.6%, and Partnership is 34.2%.

Reliability & Validity Analysis

The results of the outer loading analysis of the SEM-PLS show that there are indicators that are not valid. Invalid indicators in forming variable constructs are excluded from the data to be processed. The following table (Table 1) shows the outer loading after invalid indicators are removed.

Table 1: Outer Loading (Indicator Validity)

	Jakarta Outer Loading	Melaka Outer Loading
Organizational Readiness (X1)		
X1.01 Fund for operate		0.760
X1.02 Worker implementation		
X1.03 Think Creatively	0.834	
X1.04 Managerial support	0.847	0.673
X1.05 Resource available	0.717	0.855
Technology Readiness (X2)		
X2.01 Work well currently use	0.866	0.785
X2.02 Meet operational need	0.889	0.891
X2.03 Match requirement	0.912	0.756
X2.04 Increase efficiency	0.904	0.691
Perceived Ease of Use (X3)		
X3.01 Reduces time needed	0.776	0.910
X3.02 System is easy	0.833	0.671
X3.03 Easy to understand	0.824	0.648
X3.04 Believe ease to use	0.853	
X3.05 Learning to operate	0.708	
Perceived Usefulness (X4)		
X4.01 Use full in business	0.868	0.670
X4.02 More quickly	0.913	
X4.03 Increases the productivity	0.925	0.758
X4.04 Easier to do jobs	0.927	0.884
Perceived Trust (X5)		
X5.01 Can be trusted every time	0.900	0.737
X5.02 Security guarantees	0.934	0.959
X5.03 Can be trusted by consumers	0.927	
X5.04 System is trustworthy	0.904	
X5.05 Believe data are confidential	0.776	
X5.06 System to be reliable	0.891	
Management Character (X6)		
X6.01 Awareness of the present state	0.815	
X6.02 Awareness makes changes	0.746	0.653
X6.03 Have knowledge about	0.656	0.829
X6.04 Have knowledge in operating	0.712	0.852
X6.05 Desire to learn	0.666	0.750
E-Commerce Adoption (Z1)		
Z.01 to improve customer service	0.775	0.888
Z.02 for inventory management	0.870	0.892
Z.03 for cost reduction	0.839	0.842
Z.04 for e-trading	0.754	0.678
Z.05 for processing loan credits and banking		
Z.06 e-catalogue, and e-news	0.808	
Z.07 for bulletin board services, shared databases and directories	0.706	
Z.08 for e-payroll and e-forms	0.718	
Z.09 for book-keeping	0.834	
Z.10 for ordering and managing stock in stock	0.768	
Performance (Y1)		
Y.01 Sale growth	0.944	0.725
Y.02 Employee growth	0.759	0.877
Y.03 Number of customer growth	0.951	0.832
Y.04 Profit growth	0.937	0.819

The following are the results of Cronbach Alpha, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE), which can show the fulfillment of the reliability and validity standards of the variables (Table 2)

Table 2: Reliability & Validity Variable Analysis

Jakarta	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
X1. Organizational readiness	0.728	0.843	0.642
X2. Technology Readiness	0.915	0.940	0.797
X3. Perceived ease of use	0.859	0.899	0.641
X4. Perceived usefulness	0.929	0.950	0.826
X5. Perceived trust	0.947	0.958	0.793
X6. Management Character	0.772	0.844	0.520
Z1. E-commerce adoption	0.923	0.936	0.620
Y2. Performance	0.922	0.945	0.813
Melaka	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
X1. Organizational readiness	0.667	0.809	0.587
X2. Technology Readiness	0.816	0.864	0.615
X3. Perceived ease of use	0.690	0.793	0.566
X4. Perceived usefulness	0.665	0.817	0.601
X5. Perceived trust	0.679	0.842	0.731
X6. Management Character	0.679	0.842	0.601
Z1. E-commerce adoption	0.665	0.817	0.688
Y1. Performance	0.830	0.887	0.664

In the table above (Table 2), the Cronbach's Alpha of each construct is >0.60, the composite reliability of each construct is > 0.70, and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each construct is >0.50 which means that all constructs are reliable and valid.

Hypothesis Analysis

The hypothesis is answered by analyzing the results of the SEM-PLs test in the form of Path Analysis. In addition, it is necessary to analyze the strength of the Z1 variable which is influenced by organizational readiness (X1), technology readiness (X2), perceived ease of use (X3), perceived usefulness (X4), perceived trust (X5), (management character (X6), and an analysis of the strength of the Y (performance) variable which is influenced by the Z (e-commerce adoption) variable in the form of discrimination analysis. The following is a path analysis table (Table 3), a table of hypothesis results (Table 4), and a table of discrimination (Table 5).

Table 3: Path Analysis

Jakarta	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
X1 -> Z1	0.171	0.182	0.072	2.378	0.018
X2 -> Z1	0.262	0.258	0.148	1.771	0.077
X3 -> Z1	0.187	0.199	0.140	1.334	0.183
X4 -> Z1	0.264	0.223	0.170	1.553	0.121
X5 -> Z1	0.106	0.111	0.084	1.262	0.208
X6 -> Z1	-0.047	-0.012	0.099	0.471	0.638
Z1 -> Y1	0.490	0.496	0.074	6.596	0.000
Melaka	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
X1 -> Z1	-0.167	-0.152	0.097	1.711	0.088
X2 -> Z1	0.019	-0.008	0.119	0.164	0.870
X3 -> Z1	0.017	0.000	0.096	0.173	0.862
X4 -> Z1	-0.113	-0.099	0.088	1.290	0.198
X5 -> Z1	0.072	0.039	0.083	0.866	0.387
X6 -> Z1	0.683	0.670	0.057	11.926	0.000
Z1 -> Y1	0.200	0.223	0.090	2.219	0.027

Table 4: Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Jakarta	Melaka
H1: Organizational readiness have a significant effect on e-commerce adoption (t statistic= 2.378 > t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05)	Accepted (t statistic= 2.378> t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.018< 0.05)	Rejected (t statistic= 1.711< t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.088> 0.05)
H2: Technology readiness MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on e-commerce adoption (t statistic= 1.771< t table=1.96, Level Sig=0.05)	Rejected (t statistic= 1.771< t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.077> 0.05)	Rejected (t statistic= 0.164< t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.870> 0.05)
H3: Perceived ease of use MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on e-commerce adoption (t statistic= 1.334< t table=1.96, Level Sig=0.05)	Rejected (t statistic= 1.334< t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.183> 0.05)	Rejected (t statistic= 0.173< t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.862> 0.05)
H4: Perceived usefulness MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on e-commerce adoption (t statistic= 1.553< t table=1.96, Level Sig=0.05)	Rejected (t statistic= 1.553< t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.121> 0.05)	Rejected (t statistic= 1.290< t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.198> 0.05)
H5: Perceived trust MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on e-commerce adoption (t statistic= 1.262< t table=1.96, Level Sig=0.05)	Rejected (t statistic= 1.262< t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.208> 0.05)	Rejected (t statistic= 0.866< t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.387> 0.05)
H6: Management character of MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on e-commerce adoption (t statistic= 1.471< t table=1.96, Level Sig=0.05)	Rejected (t statistic= 0.471< t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.638> 0.05)	Accepted (t statistic= 11.926> t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.000<0.05)
H7: Adoption e-commerce by MSMEs have a significant and positive effect on MSMEs performance (t statistic= 6.596 > t table=1.96, Level Sig=0.05)	Accepted (t statistic= 6.596> t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.000<0.05)	Accepted (t statistic= 2.219> t table=1.96, Level Sig =0.05, P=0.027<0.05)

Table 5: The Coefficient of Determination

	Jakarta		Melaka	
	R Square	R Square Adjusted (R ²)	R Square	R Square Adjusted (R ²)
E-Commerce Adoption(Z)	0.624	0.607	0.528	0.501
Performance (Y)	0.240	0.235	0.040	0.031

Based on Table 5, R2 of Z1 shows that 60.7% of the Z1 variable can be explained by changes in variables X1, X2, and X3, X4, X5, X6, X7 while the other 39.3% were caused by other factors outside the model. R2 of Y1 indicates that 23.5% of the Y1 variable can be explained by changes in the variables Z1, whereas the other 76.5% is caused by factors other than the model.

Discussion Result of Jakarta and Melaka

Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use do not significantly affect the adoption of e-commerce by MSMEs in Indonesia and Malaysia. The Theory Acceptance Model formulates these two factors that influence the acceptance or failure of new technology (Davis, 1985). TAM theory formulates that it is based on individual behavior for the intention to accept new technology with two variables that are often tested in research, namely perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness (Davis (1985). However, in this study, these two variables had no effect. This is because the conditions in 1985 and the current conditions are different. In the current condition, the need for e-commerce adoption is increasing and a must. This is due to

the long and distant journey of e-commerce, as well as the changing social order that requires e-commerce as a daily part. So that the issue of acceptance of adoption is not at the level of questioning how useful it is, and whether it is useful, and only relates to attitudes towards e-commerce, but already at another level, especially regarding efforts and how MSMEs can adopt e-commerce. In addition, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are attitudes, not yet real activities, so they do not lead to e-commerce adoption efforts. This is a weakness of TAM as stated that TAM only determines the attitude toward new technologies that affects interest, not actually or not necessarily adopting new technologies (Bryan and Zuva, 2021). However, research results (Bryan and Zuva, 2021) show that TAM is used by many researchers and most of them support TAM, including the following researchers (Brandon-Jones & Katri Kauppi, 2018; Fitri & Wulandari, 2020; Noviarni, 2014). (Brandon-Jones & Katri Kauppi, 2018) examined the employee acceptance factor for the new system implemented, namely e-procurement. Two other researchers studied from the consumer side, namely consumer attitudes, and their effect on intentions. From this, it can be understood why this research and previous studies are different.

This is confirmed from the results of this study, that the factors regarding how of adopting e-commerce are shown by organizational readiness which influences the adoption of e-commerce in Jakarta, and the character of management in Melaka which has a significant effect on e-commerce adoption, where organizational readiness and management character is a requirement of doing e-commerce. In Jakarta, the organizational readiness variable with the following indicators encourages employees to think creatively, provides managerial support at all levels, and enables available resources to influence e-commerce adoption (Chaua & Denga, 2020). In Melaka, the management character variable with indicators of awareness about e-commerce, awareness to make changes, knowledge of e-commerce, knowledge of operating e-commerce technology, and desire to learn, affects the variable of e-commerce adoption. Furthermore, there are differences in the results of research in Jakarta and Melaka in this regard, because there are differences in the business scale of respondents in Jakarta and Melaka. Most respondents in Jakarta are micro-enterprises (75.9%), while the majority of Melaka respondents are small enterprises (65.8%). In Indonesia, 32.1% are MSMEs that are legal entities. In Malaysia, 64.8% are MSMEs that are legal entities. Small-scale companies and legal entities (Malaysian respondents) have greater organizational readiness compared to micro-scale companies, most of which are not legal entities (Indonesian respondents), which on the other hand do not have organizational readiness so in Indonesia organizational readiness affects e-commerce adoption. The opposite happened in Malaysia.

Likewise, management characteristics do not affect the adoption of e-commerce in micro-enterprises in Indonesia, because micro-enterprises are only operated by their owners with the help of one or two employees, this is different from the results of research in Malaysia, where small-scale businesses have more employees, and more complex management. However, organizational readiness and management character are internal factors in TOE theory. Thus, the opinion that says that TOE is only suitable for large companies, and not for SMEs (Bryan and Zuva, 2021) is not entirely true, the results of this study indicate that the two internal factors of TOE affect SMEs, although, the other factors, namely technology readiness does not take

effect. The results of this study are not entirely the same as previous studies (Zhang, 2020; Kaminski, 2020), because the object of the previous research was not MSMEs. In addition, the perception of trust has no significant effect on e-commerce adoption, both in Jakarta and Melaka. Perceive trust, like perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, is an attitude, not yet a real activity, so it does not lead to e-commerce adoption efforts. the results of this study contradict the results of research from previous researchers (Alsaedi, 2020; Punstap & Wulandari, 2020; Deng et al., 2020; Awa et al., 2016).

Furthermore, E-commerce adoption causes an increase in performance of 20%. In addition, the results of this study are following the opinion (Lee et al., 2015; Li, 2009) that the adoption of e-commerce affects financial performance and non-financial performance, as well as the development of the opinion of (Sombultawee, 2020 and Ibrahim et al. (2019) that e-commerce adoption affects financial performance. However, the results of this study are not in line with the opinion (Thomson et al., 2013) which states that although e-commerce adoption can reduce costs, adoption does not always improve performance.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study reinforce the weakness of TAM Theory that TAM Theory only emphasizes the emergence of attitudes and interests before taking real action. In addition, in conditions where the acceptance of new technology is getting wider due to the incessant development of e-commerce, TAM theory has begun to be irrelevant to be applied to e-commerce adoption. However, TAM theory is still relevant to be used for the acceptance of other new technologies, or the findings of new technologies. Where for the discovery of new technology, it is necessary to accept the attitude first. In addition, it is based on the strength of TAM Theory as evidenced by many researchers on the acceptance of new technologies. In addition, the results of this study indicate that perceived trust also does not affect e-commerce adoption. Why is that? This can be explained by the same explanation as to the two variable of TAM Theory above.

In addition, one of the factors of TOE theory, namely internal factors, has been proven to affect the adoption of e-commerce by MSMEs. However, with a different emphasis on Micro Enterprises (organizational readiness) and Small Enterprises (management characteristic). Thus, the findings of this study strengthen one of the TOE factors for technological adaptation, especially for MSEs, although it weakens other factors (technology readiness).

In addition, the adoption of e-commerce has an impact on improving the performance of MSMEs, therefore MSMEs are required to adopt e-commerce by fulfilling the factors that affect e-commerce adoption efforts, to improve their performance in order to maintain business continuity, especially in the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 (IR 4.0) which focuses on Web applications and the use of Internet technologies in business. The results of this study provide a different perspective in formulating strategies for developing SMEs in the present and in the future. The factors that influence the adoption of MSME e-commerce are organizational readiness and management characteristics, where the adoption of e-commerce affects the improvement of MSME performance. The following is the concept of the novelty of this study

(Figure 2).

The results of this study can be tested in other regions or countries to gain a better understanding of e-commerce adoption and company performance in different environmental backgrounds, it can also be used to carry out various statistical analyzes for the development of new models related to the direct and indirectly between the influencing factors, e-commerce adoption, and company performance. In addition, it is useful for policymakers in designing strategies for the development and adoption of e-commerce in the country. In particular, the government can identify important factors influencing e-commerce adoption and further establish supportive policies in enabling a greater rate of e-commerce adoption among MSMEs in the country.

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